

Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity

Didactic Materials used in teaching French in Quebec in the 19th century

Lina V. Razumova * (a), Irina V. Merzlyakova (b)

(a) *Moscow City University, 129226, Moscow (Russia), 4-1, 2nd Selskokhoziastvenny Proezd*

(b) *Transbaikal State University, 672039, Chita, (Russia), 30, Alexandro-Zavodskaya st.*

RazumovaLV@mgpu.ru

Abstract

The article examines the history of the formation of the education system in Quebec in the 19th century. This period plays an important role in the historiography of the education of the region under consideration, since at the beginning of the 19th century, the main characteristics of the system of the Quebec education system were formed, its confessional division took place, and a number of significant laws were adopted. They contribute to the formation of the structure of Quebec education, the definition of its content, as well as the content of the textbooks and teaching materials used. The latter reflect not only Quebec society and its knowledge, but also pedagogical theories and methods developed and used in foreign teaching practice, in particular in France. The article also analyzes the participation of the main social actors – the state and the Church, in the process of the formation of the general education system, it is determined that the subsequent initiatives of the state in the second half of the 19th century could not significantly affect the current situation.

Keywords: structure of Quebec education, social actors, multidimensional nature of the textbook.

© 2021 Lina V. Razumova, Irina V. Merzlyakova

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Moscow City University and peer-reviewed under responsibility of TSNI-2021 (Textbook: Focus on Students' National Identity)

Introduction

A textbook is a multifaceted phenomenon. As a subject of human activity, it constantly evolves and changes along with technical innovations, following socio-economic, political, ideological changes in

* Corresponding author. E-mail: RazumovaLV@mgpu.ru

society. As a teaching tool, the textbook is perceived as an essential tool for collecting, systematizing and transmitting human knowledge. It reflects the scientific thought of the era and attempts (albeit not always successful) to generalize and systematize it. In its instrumental function, the textbook fits into a certain pedagogical tradition, organized within the framework of specific sociopolitical institutions of society and using specific teaching methods. As a product of society, the textbook approves its value system and participates in the processes of socialization of the student. At the same time, the textbook also has a reverse effect on society with the growing influence that it acquires over time due to its increasing accessibility, democratization and mass character, the increasing separation of publishing from the political institutions of society. At all times, the textbook is at the intersection of axiological, social, political, didactic ideas. Let us point out another little-mentioned aspect of the textbook – its universal character, which it possesses from the earliest time of its existence. This universal character is due to the fact that along with the processes of Romanization and Christianization, the book, as a source of knowledge, also acquires a universal character (Riché, 1990). The textbook gains worldwide distribution thanks to the assimilation of Roman culture, and later – Christianity, which in the first millennium of its existence, as well as later, is not constrained by national borders (Meershoek, 1966). Christianity is gradually becoming a powerful factor, first ideological, and later – and linguistic unification of all territories of the Roman world, thereby ensuring its linguistic and cultural unity (Blaise, 1955). The various forms of Latin spread in Western Europe in the early Middle Ages do not know national borders: classical, school, folk, etc., which enjoy great prestige and serve as an international means of communication all branches of human life: religion, education, science, trade, politics (Mohrman, 1977). Christianity is the unifying core of the life of European medieval society. Latin is becoming the most important means of fixing knowledge in various scientific fields, many textbooks are becoming interstate circulation (Van Uytenghe, 1977).

It is Christian Latin that plays a special role in maintaining the linguistic unity of Europe for a long time (Razumova, 2019a). Colonization processes and the export of Western models of organizing education and presenting knowledge to new territories contributed to the widespread dissemination of the Western European educational system and, along with it, textbooks and teaching aids, which in different epochs and in different territories circulate in their numerous forms and names, while copy each other a lot. In part, this closeness of the principles and ideas of textbook organization is reflected, as you know, in their titles (Choppin, 2008/2013). Given these historical circumstances, we state not only the universal character that the textbook is acquiring as a leading teaching tool, but also the fact that a fairly unified «educational market» is gradually being created in Europe, creating and using unified teaching aids: dictionaries, grammars, textbooks, alphabets, syllabaries, etc. And although the linguistic unity of Europe is lost with the beginning of the use of national languages in the 15-17 centuries as tools of linguistic description in

textbooks, yet the generality of didactic principles set forth in educational literature continues to be supported for a long time by Latin book samples. Due to its substantial and formal diversity, as well as its functional significance in society, the textbook is an interesting object of research. We emphasize at the same time that, despite its versatility and historical polymorphism, the textbook has long been perceived as a kind of well-defined, obvious object of research that does not need additional definitions. At the same time, such definitions are necessary and will be made by us later in the article on the material of the evolution of French textbooks used in the 19th century on the territory of Quebec.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The main purpose of this analysis is the historical analysis of the formation of the Francophone education system in Quebec. The sociocultural and political contexts that played a decisive role in the formation of the system of Quebec francophone education, developing in a situation of social and linguistic contact, are studied. The main legislative acts in the field of education are presented, which have determined for a long time the strategic directions for the development of education in this province, its form, structure and types of developed didactic materials.

Literature review

The textbook concept is a historically recent concept. Those editions that today fall into the category of textbooks and educational literature were not considered as such for a long time. So, in French society before the Great French Revolution, there is no common name for the literature used in the learning process. We note a similar situation in all countries of Western Europe, where the textbook exists in its most diverse titles and versions, referring to: 1) the form of organization of the material: antologia (Portuguese); florilegio (Italian) recueil, jardin (French), 2) the idea of a whole, consisting of parts: compendio (Spanish, Portuguese), précis, abrégé, tableau, 3) role performed: mentor, guide (French), Hilfsbuch (German) , 4) the concept of «hand», to what is at hand and what is convenient to carry is contained in the following titles of textbooks: руководство (Russian), manuel (French), manuales escolares (Spanish), manuali per la scuola (Italian), manual școlar (Romanian), příručka (Czech), podręcznik (Polish.), rokas gramata (Latin), Handbuch (German) 5) teaching method: method (English), méthode, cours (French), which receives a number of positive definitions: facile, rapide, complète, nouvelle, etc. 6) The method of organizing the material is often indicated, going from simple to complex: rudiments (French), nociones (Spanish), elements (English) or the material medium on which the book is written: tavola, palette (Italian), Tableta (Spanish). 7) The didactic function of learning is emphasized in the following names: Lehrbuch (German), Lerebok (Norwegian), didaskaleion (Greek <didaskēin – to teach),

livro didatico (Portuguese), eddirasat kitab (Arabic <eddirasat – to teach), учебник (in all Slavic languages, from teach, study). 8) The goal of teaching reading is realized in numerous alphabets, drop caps, syllables and books for reading: alphabets, abécédaire, sillabaire (French), Alphabetare (Greek.), ABC-Buch (German), Abbecedario (Italian), букварь, азбука (Russian, Bel., Ukrainian), Lesebuch (German), libro de lectura (Spanish), readers (English), livro de leitura (Portuguese), etc. (Chopin, 2008/2013).

And today it is not always easy to determine whether a book is a textbook? The complexity of this task stems from the fact that not only are there no general criteria for defining a textbook (Zagriazkina, 2019), but also due to the fact that it is necessary to consider a large corpus of books and publications for which the criteria for their inclusion or exclusion from the number of textbooks must be determined (Vikulova, Serebrennikova, Gerasimova, 2020). Considered in a diachronic aspect, which is able to reveal structural and content changes in the phenomenon under study, this goal becomes even more complex.

In this regard, we will refer to the textbook any specially designed textbook, as well as all accompanying texts (reference materials: books for the teacher, the student's notebook, additional manuals and dictionaries used in the practice of teaching in classroom and homework), intended for a specific level of education and containing knowledge in a specific field of activity and methods of mastering this knowledge, as well as a certain value paradigm, developed in accordance with the values of the society in which the textbook functions.

An analysis of the socio-historical characteristics of the development of the Quebec francophone education system shows that the Church plays the main role in its formation in the 19th century (Audet, 1969). During this time, 11 religious congregations operate in Quebec. They set up their own private religious educational institutions, work in already existing Catholic schools, often in rural parishes that are difficult to access and remote from cities (Dumont, Malouin, 1983). Educational policy is formed in the process of interaction between two linguistic and religious-ethnic groups – Francophones-Catholics and Anglophones-Protestants (Razumova, 2019b). The development of the structure of the education system and didactic aids used in teaching is carried out with the widest involvement of Western European samples, in particular French (Razumova, 2016), proving once again the universality of didactic ideas and educational systems and didactic materials developed on their basis. The development of the educational system of Quebec as a whole, as well as the textbooks used in the learning process, is moving from a wide inclusion of a religious component to an increasingly secular type of education (Razumova, 2016). This is reflected in the structure of the training system and the content of the developed training materials.

Methodology

To solve the set tasks, a comparative-historical method is used, based on the cultural-historical interpretation of data, an assessment of educational policies developed in Quebec, the participation of social actors in the formation of the Quebec education system and the development of educational and didactic literature. Its application allowed obtaining the following scientific results.

During the 19th century, the Canadian government developed and adopted about 20 legislative acts in the field of education, but only a few of them really contribute to its radical changes. Let us point out, as an example, the law on the so-called royal schools (1801) and the law on general secular schools (1841), according to which the Catholic francophone school had to exist, despite a number of approved by these laws provisions, only on donations from parents. This circumstance, as well as the refusal of the state to finance the previously opened Catholic francophone schools, aroused the just outrage of the francophone population. A real instrument of state assistance in organizing the education system in the province is the law on factory schools, adopted in 1824, and its subsequent amendments (Razumova, 2016). It establishes the responsibility of the state for partial financing (50%) of the education system, its control of the content of education, the introduction of public semester examinations (addition of 1830), the division of the province of Quebec into educational districts. The same law determines the educational age of students (supplement 1831), decisions are made in the field of training teachers. For this, it was planned to open a number of higher schools (*écoles normales*) in the cities of Quebec, Trois Rivieres and Montreal (Dufour, 1997).

Despite the discriminatory terms of funding offered by the English government for francophone Catholic schools, the emergence of the education system in Quebec bears witness to its unprecedented growth: primary education in parish francophone schools covered about 50% of all school-age children (Dufour, 1997). The main stages of school education in the last third of the 19th century are: the initial stage, most often denoted by the term *cours élémentaire* (3-4 years), the middle stage (*cours modèle*, *cours intermédiaire*, *cours moyen* – 2-3 years), as well as the highest step (*cours supérieur* – on average 2-3 years). One- and two-year courses (*cours gradués*) are optional. The full course of school education was on average 8 years, and together with additional courses – 9-10 years. The level of education of women in rural areas was more often higher than the level of education of men due to the early entry into working life of the latter.

In parallel with the general education system, from the 70s of the 19th century, a vocational education system was created, represented by vocational schools (*écoles de métiers*) (offering elementary vocational education), schools (*écoles techniques*) (offering secondary vocational education), short-term vocational courses (*cours*) (Audet, 1969).

Distinctive features of publishing activities for the release of school literature in Quebec are: 1) the participation of the church in the preparation and publication of school textbooks, 2) the use of textbooks published abroad (France and England) in educational practice.

The main publishers and suppliers of textbooks from France and England are the clergy, various religious brotherhoods, and secular publishing houses. The religious congregation La «Brotherhood of Christian Schools» («La Communauté des frères des Ecoles chrétiennes») has been a prominent actor throughout the 19th century in the preparation and publication of educational literature for the French-speaking schools in Quebec. Founded in the 17th century in Lyon and actively engaged in the preparation of educational literature and publishing in France before the French Revolution, the brotherhood resumes its activities in the early 19th century in Quebec, thus acting as an important link between the former colony and the metropolis, ensuring the continuity of the Western European system education in New France. The surviving correspondence of the fraternity, as well as the lists of literature published by the fraternity, make it possible to determine the types of textbooks that were published and used in the practice of Francophone Quebec teaching. Thus, «The Treatise on the Duties of a Christian» («Traité des devoirs du Chrétien»), published at the end of the 17th century, was reprinted more than once in France, and a century and a half later, that is, in the middle of the 19th century, it became one of the most popular books in Quebec. Subsequently, it served as the basis for the creation of numerous books for reading in Catholic Francophone schools. A book of prayers (livre de prières), a syllabarium (sillabaire), a book for reading (livre de lecture), a history textbook (traité de civilité), a collection of psalms (psautier) are the main teaching materials of the Quebec parish schools in the first half of the 19th century. They are the ones most often ordered and imported by the Brotherhood of Christian Schools to Quebec in the form of books published in whole or in part in France. Thus, the first 12 French grammars used in Quebec between 1840 and 1881 are reprinted French grammars (Dumont, Malouin, 1983).

The project of creating common schools, although it was not implemented, contributed to the revision of the content of education: the study time allotted for religious instruction is gradually being reduced (in the senior grades it takes no more than half an hour a day), new subjects are being introduced: physics, mathematics, history, drawing, singing, manual labor. At the end of the 19th century, the need to study English as a second language was recognized: in elementary school, half an hour a day is allotted for its study, in high school – one hour, in high school – two hours a day. There is an increasing secularization of the Quebec francophone education.

In the second half of the 19th century, religious and secular publishing houses in Quebec began to develop their own textbooks in various disciplines. Thus, at this time, the Brotherhood of Christian Schools

published textbooks on general and Canadian history, arithmetic, algebra, geometry, drawing, manual labor, and agriculture. A significant place in the brotherhood's activities for the development and publication of school literature is occupied by the French language, issues of its teaching and a number of its aspects: grammar, reading, spelling. As an example, we point to the following textbooks: *Exercices d'orthographe en rapport avec la dernière édition de la grammaire élémentaire* (1888), *Grammaire du premier âge avec exercices faciles* (1892), *Corrigé de quelques exercices de la grammaire du premier âge* (?), *Cours pratique de langue française: grammaire et composition: cours moyen* (1899), *Livre de lecture courante: cours élémentaire* (1896), *Livre de lecture courante: cours moyen* (1897), *Méthode de lecture: syllabaire* (1897), *Lecture à haute voix. Etudes théorique et pratique de la prononciation française* (1900), *La lecture française: comment l'enseigner aux cours élémentaire, moyen et supérieur* (?) and many others.

Due to the dialectophone majority of France and the diglossy of colloquial and normalized speech in Quebec, French in its standardized form does not appear at the beginning of the 19th century as a national language either in the former metropolis or in its former colony, revealing the need to develop effective methods and school tools for teaching it. This linguistic situation makes it obvious that we understand the fact that school grammar cannot act as a kind of logical and obvious continuation of grammar as a science. In France and Quebec, it becomes a means of mass education for a practically unfamiliar speaker, a different, normalized written French language, significantly different from spoken language, dialects of France and the spoken language of Quebec. The general vector of changes (however, with constant fluctuations) in the understanding of school grammar can be designated as follows: from a grammar of a universalist type, based on the laws of logical thinking, to a grammar of a functionalist type, based on a description of the functions of linguistic phenomena. In the first half of the 19th century, there is an intermediate form that tries to combine these two types of grammars. We are talking, for example, about the grammar of Chapsal, which is actively copied by Quebec authors, in particular, by the Abbot T. Maguire in his famous grammar, published in 1941.

Grammar is understood by many authors broadly in accordance with the previously existing grammatical tradition and includes teaching phonetics, spelling, acquaintance with parts of speech, difficult cases of lexical use. Particular attention is paid to the problems of spelling, which are designed to show the difference between oral and written forms of speech. These sections organize the content of many grammars used in school practice in France and Quebec.

The contacting of two language groups in Quebec, Anglophones and Francophones, borrowings from English determine the need to include one more section – borrowings from English, which become constant in all Quebec grammars and dictionaries of the 19th century. In this regard, the creation of a high-quality

usus is seen by Quebec grammarians not only in the rejection of the use of vernacular and dialectal linguistic elements, but also in the rejection of English borrowings. It is the standardization of vocabulary that is perceived as a primary task in the framework of most textbooks of the French language of the second half of the 19th century, which include lists of condemned Anglicisms and cripples from English (*des anglicismes à combattre*), and which are aimed at acquaintance with the French equivalents of many English loanwords (textbooks by E. Blanchard).

Results

Let us state that, as a multidimensional phenomenon, a textbook is simultaneously related to pedagogy, politics, the Church, economics, sociology, publishing and other branches of human activity. It is a concentrated expression of society and many of its institutions and ideas. Taking into account this relationship is a prerequisite in the process of studying any national education system.

Defining the nature of education in Quebec in the 19th century, we state that during this period the clergy played the main role in the spread of education in this province. It is trying to create an educational market in accordance with its own vision of the role and content of education in Quebec society in the conditions of complete inattention to the problems of francophone education on the part of the state. The textbooks and teaching materials he creates follow the best Western European and, in particular, French educational literature and are interesting, well-structured teaching aids. They contain a modern vision of the scientific problems of those disciplines that were introduced into school education throughout the 19th century. These include algebra, geometry, geography, history, drawing, French and a number of others. Their inclusion in curricula and the gradual reduction in the time for studying religious disciplines signify a gradual transition from a religious education to an education that is more and more secular in its content. The influence of France and Western European educational models is also great in the field of borrowing the teaching methods used in teaching. The 19th century was marked by a gradual transition to a functionalist teaching paradigm.

Discussions

Clarifying the provision on the contacts between Quebec and France and the influence of France on the Quebec system of becoming universal education, we emphasize that the relationship between Quebec and France did not end after the transfer of Quebec to England in 1763. The absence of official political relations with France to a certain extent is compensated for during this period by active intellectual cooperation in the field of education, book publishing and preparation of school textbooks. The influence of France can be traced in the field of 1) the provision and preparation of educational literature, 2) the use of

samples of textbooks in various disciplines, 3) in the preparation of authors of textbooks, 4) determining the structure of the developed education system.

Conclusion

The ideological context of the formation of the education system in Quebec was marked in the 19th century by the struggle of the Catholic Church and the British state for control over education. This is reflected in the content of many laws on education adopted in the 19th century, as well as in a number of socio-political movements of that time.

Religious institutions of the Quebec society played a positive role in overcoming the educational crisis of the general francophone education system, which contributed to the gradual formation of a multi-level system of francophone education in Quebec, the creation of most textbooks and teaching materials used in the education system. French grammars of Duviivier, Chambaut, Lomond, Chapsal, dictionaries of the French Academy of Sciences are becoming reference sources that are widely used in the school practice of teaching French in Quebec, as well as samples on the basis of which local school textbooks are created. Their creative processing allows us to get away from the etymologizing principle of traditional grammatical descriptions and include *usus*, observation of real speech as a central element of creating a normalized form of language, including it as a positive (linguistic standard of French in France) or negative language material (colloquial *usus* of Quebec) in school grammars.

References

- Aubin, P. (2000). La pénération des manuels scolaire de France au Québec. Un cas type: Les frères des Ecoles chrétiennes, XIX–e–XX–e siècles. *Histoire de l'éducation*, 85, 3–24.
- Audet, L.-Ph.; Gautier, Ph.-A. (1969). Le système scolaire du Québec: organisation et fonctionnement.
- Blaise, A. (1955). Manuel du latin chrétien. Strasbourg: Brepols.
- Choppin, A. (2008; 2013). Le manuel scolaire, une fausse évidence historique. *Histoire de l'éducation*, 117. Retrieved from <http://journals.openedition.org/histoire-education/565>
- Dufour, A. (1997). Histoire de l' l'éducation au Québec. Québec : Editions du Boréal.
- Dumont, M., Malouin M. (1983). M. Evolution et rôle des congrégations religieuses enseignantes féminines au Québec, 1840–1960. *S.C.H.E.C. Sessions d'étud*, 50, 201–230.

- Meershoek, G. Q. (1966). *Le latin biblique d'après Saint Jérôme. Aspects linguistiques de la rencontre entre la Bible et le monde classique.* Nijmegen – Utrecht: Editions Dekker & Van de Vegt.
- Mohrmann, Ch. (1977). *Eludes sur le latin des chrétiens.* Rome: Edizioni di Storia e Letteratura.
- Razumova, L. V. (2016). Representation of the language norm in French language variants outside of France (Quebec and Belgian variants). Abstract of the dissertation of the Doctor of Philology. *Moscow: Moscow State Pedagogical University.*
- Razumova, L. V. (2019 a). Functional features of the Latin language in Western Europe in the IV-X centuries. *Sovremennye issledovaniya social'nyh problem. Sbornik nauchnyh statej. Yazykoznanie [Modern studies of social problems. Collection of scientific articles. Linguistics]*, 11 (5-1), 279-287.
- Razumova, L. V. (2019 b). The system of francophone education in Quebec in the XVII-XIX centuries. *Pedagogika i psihologiya obrazovaniya. Sbornik nauchnyh trudov Moskovskogo pedagogicheskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta [Pedagogy and Psychology of education. Collection of scientific papers. Moscow: Publishing House of the Moscow Pedagogical State University]*, 2, 15-22.
- Riché, P. (1990). Reflexions sur l'histoire de l'éducation dans le Haut Moyen Age. *Histoire de l'éducation*, 50, 17–38.
- Van Uytfanghe, M. (1977). Latin mérovingien, latin carolingien et rustica romana lingua : continuité ou discontinuité. *Revue de l'Université de Bruxelles. Actes du Colloque international pluridisciplinaire organisé par l'Institut des Hautes Études de Belgique*, 65–88.
- Vikulova, L.G., Serebrennikova, E.F., Gerasimova, S.A. (2020). Educational and didactic discourse: an instrumental and pragmatic approach to solving problems of intercultural communication. *Pedagogicheskij diskurs: kachestvo rechi uchitelya*, 70-76.
- Zagriazkina, T.Y. (2019). The language and culture of the national tradition of learning french, or the myth of eternal return? *Uchitel'. Uchenik. Uchebnik.* Moscow: KDU.